

Thermal Stability of Valuable Metals in Lithium-Ion Battery Cathode Materials: Temperature Range 100-400 °C

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Abstract

Lithium is crucial in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), serving as a main component of the electrolyte and cathode. Elements such as cobalt, nickel, and manganese are also vital for high performance, energy density, and stability. This study aimed to examine the behaviour of end-of-life cathode material (NMC622) and its valuable metals after exposure to temperatures between 100 and 400 °C, comparing it with untreated material. The lithium content cannot be reliably determined by conventional analytical methods, so inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was chosen for this purpose. For ICP-OES measurements, samples were dissolved in different solvents for a specified time, and the concentrations of lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt were measured. From the measured values, their theoretical yields were calculated. Due to the annealing at given temperatures and subsequent dissolution, this step can be considered as the first stage of the pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical process used in battery recycling. The study was complemented by further analyses to monitor the effect of annealing temperatures on the properties of the material. Based on the results, it was found that the highest theoretical yield in this temperature range was for material annealed at 400 °C and dissolved in 20% nitric acid for 4 hours.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are considered the most powerful energy storage system for portable electronic devices, wireless devices, hybrid power and electric vehicles (EVs) due to their long life, high energy density, and high voltage [1-3]. For this reason, the LIB industry is one of the fastest growing industries in the world, but the scarce raw materials such as lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt make it essential to manage these resources effectively. There are various approaches to sustainability in this sector, including battery reuse and recycling. As the amount of spent batteries increases, the waste management will need to be systematically addressed. Recycling is becoming crucial for the renewability of scarce elements [4-6]. An efficient way to dispose of spent LIBs is a key factor for industrial battery manufacturers and recyclers. This is important due to the limited resources of strategic metals, the potential negative environmental impact, and the potential to obtain high economic benefits [2, 6].

The basic description of a battery cell involves the use of the relationship between the cell potential and the concentrations of individual components. This is described by the Nernst equation (see Equation 1),

$$\Delta E = \Delta E^0 + \frac{kT}{v_e e} \ln \frac{a_{Ox}}{a_{Red}} \quad (1)$$

where k [JK^{-1}] represents the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature [K], v_e is the number of electrons exchanged, and e stands for elementary charge [C]. The electrode potential ΔE is then described using the natural logarithm of the ratio of chemical activities of the relevant oxidised and reduced components in the system and the standard electrode potential ΔE^0 [7, 8].

In essence, LIBs can be defined as energy storage systems that operate through the process of lithium-ion insertion reactions occurring at both the positive and negative electrodes, where lithium ions serve as the charge carriers. This broad categorisation encompasses various cell chemistries that collectively constitute the LIB family. The majority of LIBs typically feature a negative electrode primarily composed of materials such as carbon (e.g., graphite), lithium titanate ($\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$) or innovative materials like metallic lithium and Li(Si) alloys. The choice of electrolyte can vary depending on the electrode materials selected, but typically comprises a blend of lithium salts (e.g. LiPF_6) and an organic solvent (e.g. diethyl carbonate) to facilitate ion transfer. To facilitate the passage of lithium ions between electrodes while preventing the occurrence of internal short circuits, a separating membrane is employed [9-11]. Known examples of materials used as cathodes include lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO_2), lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) (which can be coated with Ga or SiO_2), lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide ($\text{Li}(\text{Ni}_{1-x-y}\text{Mn}_x\text{Co}_y)\text{O}_2$), lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide ($\text{Li}(\text{Ni}_{1-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Al}_y)\text{O}_2$), and lithium manganese oxide (LiMn_2O_4) [12-15].

The predominant cathode materials used in LIBs for EVs are part of a category of layered mixed transition metal oxide compounds characterised by rhombohedral symmetry (D_{3d}^5 space group). These compounds are represented by the formula $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$ (with $(x + y) \in [0,1]$) and are commonly called NMC [16-18]. The principle of NMC cathode materials lies in the combination of nickel and manganese, each contributing specific attributes. Nickel is known for its high specific energy, but has the drawback of poor stability, while manganese possesses the advantage of forming a spinel structure to reduce internal resistance, though it offers lower specific energy. The specific combination of these metals, nickel and manganese, varies among manufacturers and is closely guarded as a proprietary formula. Researchers are actively exploring nickel-rich electrodes to enhance energy density while reducing the cobalt content to reduce costs. Companies have transitioned from NMC111 to NMC442, NMC622, NMC721 and now anticipate the introduction of NMC811 [9, 19, 20].

The theoretical capacity of stoichiometric NMC materials is around $275 \text{ mAh} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$, though its accessible capacity depends on the ratio of transition-metal ions within the material. Within the layered transition metal oxide category, cathodes rich in nickel, such as NMC811, exhibit higher capacity and operational voltage, with nickel as the primary active redox species ($\text{Ni}^{2+} \leftrightarrow \text{Ni}^{4+}$). However, nickel-rich compounds often exhibit poor thermal stability. Manganese plays a crucial role in the preservation of battery cycle life and safety, while cobalt enhances electronic conductivity, improving rate capability. Commercially, NMC111 and NMC333 have reached a more mature stage, incorporating the benefits of various transition metals [21]. For nickel-rich NMC materials, the accessible capacity is significantly higher than NMC111 but faces challenges such as cation mixing [22], surface reconstruction to rock salt [23], phase transformation [24], particle cracking [25], transition metal dissolution [26] and parasitic reactions with electrolyte [27].

Cathode scrap stands out as the most precious element for recovery in the context of spent LIBs, given its abundance of valuable metals such as lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt. Consequently, a well-defined framework has been put in place to facilitate its retrieval. Nowadays, the techniques employed to recycle cathode scrap mainly encompass hydrometallurgical methods, pyrometallurgical methods, combined pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical methods, and innovative techniques such as molten salt or deep eutectic solvent methods [1, 28-30].

This work focused on the behaviour of the end-of-life cathode material NMC622 from LIB cell when exposed to different temperatures. The key point was to determine the content of valuable metals that are released from the material with increasing temperature. This can then determine the temperature at which the highest yield of valuable metals will be obtained for possible further processing. Therefore, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was chosen as the main analysis, which is one of the few methods that can quantitatively determine the lithium content of the material. Other monitored elements were nickel, manganese, and cobalt. A whole set of samples was prepared and annealed for 1 hour each at temperatures of 100-800 °C, however, due to the number of results obtained, this paper focuses only on temperatures of 100-400 °C and the results dealing with the behaviour of the material at temperatures of 500-800 °C will be described in following article. For ICP-OES measurements, the material was dissolved in two different solvents, namely nitric acid and demineralized water. Demineralized water was chosen due to its safety, low economic cost, and also because lithium has the potential to be recovered by water. Material that has not been exposed to heat was used as a reference sample. In order to get a comprehensive picture of the material behaviour at different temperatures, other methods were used, namely X-ray diffraction (XRD) and fluorescence (XRF), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDS). Thus, the results described below represent a comprehensive material analysis of the end-of-life NMC622.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Materials

Chemicals

Nitric acid (HNO_3) used in this study was of analytical grade and was purchased from Lach-Ner, s.r.o. (Neratovice, Czech Republic). The single element lithium standard (99,99% Li_2CO_3 in 2% HNO_3 , ANALYTIKA, s.r.o., Czech Republic) and the multi-element standard of 26

elements (in 5% HNO₃, ANALYTIKA, s.r.o., Czech Republic) were used as calibration standards for ICP-OES measurements.

2.2 Methods

Disassembly procedure

The LIB module, which is commonly used in battery electric vehicles (BEVs), was selected for material analysis. This module consists of 24 NMC pouch cells, each cell has a voltage of 3.65 V and a capacity of 78 Ah, which create the base for the nominal module voltage of 29.36 V. The module was short-circuited to ensure safe handling prior to disassembly, and was then manually disassembled into its individual parts, i.e. milling off the aluminium casing, removing the polyurethane and polymer materials used as electrical and thermal insulation. The remaining plastic and metal coverings were then removed and the individual cells separated [31].

Sample preparation

The LIB pouch cell was disassembled into individual layers of cathodes, anodes, and separators. The cathode material including the aluminium foil was manually cut into square pieces with a size of 25 × 25 mm. These samples were placed in a porcelain crucible and heat treated in an electric furnace at a temperature of 100, 200, 300 and 400 °C for 60 min with a temperature gradient of 5 °C/min in air atmosphere. The samples were labelled according to the firing temperature (e.g. a sample treated at 100 °C for one hour is named NMC101, etc.). A reference sample that was not exposed to heat treatment is labelled as NMC0. For ICP-OES analysis, the burnt cathode material was finely cut with scissors into strips with a defined area of 17.5 ± 2.5 mm². The samples were then dissolved in 25 mL of demineralized water or 20% nitric acid solution, respectively, for 1.5, 2 and 4 hours. The suspension was diluted 500 times, filtered, and analysed by ICP-OES.

Two samples were selected for X-ray diffraction and fluorescence analyses - NMC0 as reference material and a sample annealed at 400 °C (NMC401). The NMC401 sample was placed in 80 mL of distilled water in a plastic container. A SONOPULS HD 2200.2 ultrasonic homogeniser with an ultrasonic generator GM 2200.2 and an ultrasonic converter UW 2200 (all BANDELIN, Germany) was used for separation. The amplitude was set to 30%, the sonication time was 2 × 5 minutes. The distilled water was poured through a sieve to separate the aluminium parts, and the poured distilled water containing NMC particles was evaporated in an evaporating dish in an oven at 95 °C to constant weight. The dried powdered material was ground in an agate pestle and mortar to obtain a fine powder. The NMC0 sample could not be separated, so it was analysed as a compact sample.

X-ray fluorescence analysis

X-ray fluorescence analysis was conducted using an Axios sequential wavelength-dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WD-XRF) spectrometer. The instrument used for the analysis was equipped with an Rh anode end-window X-ray tube of type 4GN, featuring a 75 µm Be window. Acquisition of peak intensity data was performed using the SuperQ 5.0 software. The measurements were made under vacuum conditions. The generator settings-collimator-crystal-detector combinations were optimised for collecting 11 scans for all 83 measured elements, for many elements are more than one X-ray line available. The collected data were subsequently processed and quantified using Omnia standard analysis software. The measurement time was about 20 min.

Scanning electron microscopy

The scanning electron microscope TESCAN VEGA 3 LMU (SEM) in secondary electron (SE) and backscattered electron (BSE) modes was used to determine the composition of the materials used and measure their particle size (VEGA3 software). The OXFORD Instruments INCA 350 EDS analyser enables chemical microanalysis of the observed sample, which is then evaluated in the AZtec software version 4.4. The composition was repeatedly measured on an area of 0.005 mm².

X-ray diffraction analysis

X-ray powder diffraction measurements were conducted at room temperature using a PANanalytical X'Pert PRO θ - θ powder diffractometer featuring parafocusing Bragg-Brentano geometry, and CoK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.79028 \text{ \AA}$) at a 35 kV X-ray tube voltage and a current of 40 mA. Data acquisition utilised a high-speed detector X'Celerator. Subsequent data analysis and interpretation were carried out using the software package HighScore Plus 4.0.

Thermal properties

Thermogravimetric measurement was performed on Discovery TGA550 Auto Advanced in air atmosphere (air, technical grade, SIAD s.r.o.) at heating rate 10 °C/min from room temperature to 1000 °C, sample weight approximately 15 mg.

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES)

The concentrations of elements of Li, Ni, Mn and Co were determined by the inductively coupled plasma emission spectrometer 5900 ICP-OES (Agilent, USA). The plasma was generated from the Ar flow using a water-cooled semiconductor radiofrequency generator with a frequency of 27 Hz and a power of 1.2 kW. The measurements were performed in the so-called synchronous vertical dual view (SVDV) mode, which allows measurements in axial and radial views simultaneously. Quantitative analysis was based on a five-point calibration series for each measured element, ranging from 0.2 to 1.0 mg/L. The results are based on three measurements of each sample.

3. Results

Composition and structure

Composition and structure using XRF and XRD were used to monitor changes between the initial sample (NMC0) and the material annealed to the highest temperature observed (NMC401). More detailed changes observed for each sample (NMC0-NMC401) were recorded using SEM/EDS.

The XRF analysis of the chemical composition (see Table 1) identified nickel oxide (56.2 wt.%), manganese oxide (13.4 wt.%) and cobalt oxide (11.7 wt.%) as the major elements. Other minor elements were aluminium, which corresponds to the material from which the current collector is made, phosphorus, and fluorine, which come from other parts of the battery, such as electrolytes or binder used for the cathode material. Another identified minor element was tungsten. It is likely a dopant in the form of, for example, tungsten oxide (WO₃), aimed at improving electron conductivity and enhancing the kinetics of redox reactions in cathode materials [30].

Some differences can be observed in the composition of the NMC0 and NMC401 samples. While for some elements (phosphorus, fluorine, and tungsten), there was a decrease in their

content as a result of heat exposure, for others there was an increase. The decrease in fluorine and phosphorus is due to electrolyte leaching and partial degradation of the binder. As a result, the content of the major elements increased.

Table 1

Chemical composition in wt.% analysed by XRF in the reference material (NMC0) and in the heat-treated material (NMC401).

Analysed composition [wt.%]	Sample	
	NMC0	NMC401
Al ₂ O ₃	0.6 ± 0.0	7.0 ± 0.1
P ₂ O ₅	2.3 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.0
F	15.2 ± 0.6	2.9 ± 0.2
MnO	13.4 ± 0.1	14.4 ± 0.1
Co ₃ O ₄	11.7 ± 0.1	12.9 ± 0.1
NiO	56.2 ± 0.2	61.3 ± 0.1
WO ₃	0.6 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0

The results of SEM/EDS (refer to Table 2) are consistent with the results obtained from XRF. From the results of the EDS analysis, a more noticeable decrease in fluorine content was observed, specifically between samples exposed to 300 °C (NMC301) and 400 °C (NMC401). This again corresponds to an increase in major element content.

Table 2

The chemical composition of the cathode material at different thermal exposures performed by EDS, given in wt.%.

Element	Sample				
	NMC0	NMC101	NMC201	NMC301	NMC401
Al	0.5 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.1
F	19.9 ± 0.1	20.6 ± 0.5	20.7 ± 0.2	20.8 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.3
Ni	30.2 ± 0.1	26.9 ± 1.1	29.6 ± 0.2	32.0 ± 0.2	47.9 ± 1.7
Mn	9.4 ± 0.1	9.1 ± 0.4	9.2 ± 0.1	9.9 ± 0.1	14.2 ± 0.8
Co	7.2 ± 0.1	6.8 ± 0.6	7.0 ± 0.1	7.7 ± 0.1	12.3 ± 1.1
W	1.2 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.2
P	0.6 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.1	0.60 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	0.8 ± 0.1
C	9.0 ± 0.2	9.0 ± 1.4	9.3 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.2	3.7 ± 0.4
O	22.1 ± 0.1	23.8 ± 0.6	22.0 ± 0.1	18.8 ± 0.1	16.9 ± 0.6

Scanning electron microscope images of the cathode material surface (see Fig. 1) were taken in the secondary electron (SE) and backscattered electron (BSE) modes. The left half of the images always shows SE, while the right half shows the signals detected by BSE. It can be seen in the images that as the annealing temperature of the sample increases, the polymer binder decreases, and the structure of the spinel particles becomes visible.

a)

b)

Fig. 1. SEM pictures taken from samples (a) NMC101; (b) NMC201; (c) NMC301; (d) NMC401.

X-ray diffraction analysis (see Fig. 2) conclusively verified the crystalline phases of NMC622, both in the initial form (NMC0) and after exposure to a thermal treatment at 400 °C (NMC401). In the thermally treated sample, additional crystalline phases, namely LiF and NiO, were discerned. LiF comes from the electrolyte, and NiO comes from the decomposing lithium-

nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide. Subsequent chemical analysis, as detailed in Table 1, revealed NiO, MnO, and Co₃O₄ as predominant oxides, with NMC0 exhibiting a relatively elevated fluorine content compared to the NMC401 specimen. This disparity aligns with the characteristics of the binder used, which exhibits a higher melting point. Other elements or oxides were present only in marginal proportions.

Fig. 2. XRD analysis of NMC0 and NMC401.

Thermal analysis

Thermogravimetric measurement of sample NMC0 in air atmosphere (Fig. 3) showed a small weight loss up to 230 °C which is attributed to electrolyte loss. The decomposition between 230 and 630 °C took place in two main steps with peaks at 270 and 540 °C; the loss in this interval is mainly attributed to the decomposition of the present polymers. Significant thermooxidation, followed by mass loss, was observed at temperatures above 750 °C. Most of the observed changes occur outside our studied temperature range (above 400 °C).

Fig. 3. TGA curve of the sample NMC0.

Concentrations of Li, Ni, Mn, and Co

The results of the ICP-OES analysis showed that the measured concentration depends on the dissolution time, the type of solvent, and the temperature to which the initial material was exposed. In a 20% HNO₃ solution (see Fig. 4), the measured concentrations were several times higher than in demineralized water. In terms of the dependence of the measured concentration on the dissolution time, the highest values were measured after 4 hours, however, after 2 hours of dissolution, in some cases the relevant ions were possibly precipitated, resulting in a decrease in the concentration. The temperature to which the initial material was exposed before dissolution also plays an important role, as can be seen from the graphs, the concentrations of Ni, Mn, and Co are significantly higher in the case of material exposed to temperatures of 300 and 400 °C, respectively. This is probably related to the melting temperature of the binder used in the manufacture of the batteries. Nickel was the most leached element from the NMC material, followed by manganese, cobalt, and the lowest values were measured for lithium. The mean relative standard deviations were 0.24% for lithium, 0.31% for nickel, 0.42% for manganese and 0.39% for cobalt.

Fig. 4. Concentration of (a) lithium; (b) nickel; (c) manganese and (d) cobalt dissolved in 20% HNO₃.

Demineralized water was chosen as the second type of solvent because it is much safer to use than acids. After dissolution in demineralized water, only lithium concentrations were measured (see Fig. 5), which were almost constant after 2 hours of dissolution. For the other elements, it would be appropriate to choose a different procedure or solvent type for quantitative analysis due to the values that were below the detection limit of the instrument. The mean relative standard deviation was 0.31%.

Fig. 5. Concentration of lithium dissolved in demineralized water.

Theoretical valuable metal yield

To determine the yield, the maximal theoretical amount was computed utilising the technical datasheet specifications. The cathode material composes 42.5% of a cell. Therefore from

$$m_{cathode} = m_{pack} \cdot \frac{p}{100} \quad (2)$$

where p is a portion of the active cathode material, and the cathode mass of a cell is

$$M_{cathode} = 0.458 \text{ kg} \quad (3)$$

The mole and mass quantities of individual elements of $\text{Li}_{1.0}\text{Ni}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ were calculated based on formula

$$n_A = u_A \cdot \frac{m_{cathode}}{M_{cathode}} \quad (4)$$

where n_A is the number of moles of the respective element, u_A is the stoichiometric coefficient [4]. From the mass concentration measured by ICP-OES, the mass of dissolved ions was calculated for the highest measured concentrations, in this case for samples dissolved for 4 hours (see Table 3a). From this mass, the theoretical yield of valuable metals obtained by dissolution in 20% nitric acid solution and demineralized water, respectively, was calculated. The results shown (see Table 3b) are for the NMC401 sample after 4 hours of dissolution.

The masses of dissolved valuable metals increase with increasing annealing temperature of the sample. The highest results are obtained for the sample annealed at 400 °C. The dissolution in nitric acid gave a lithium yield almost five times higher than that obtained in demineralized water.

The efficiency of this method was compared with the available results of the hydrometallurgical method. The highest recovery (91%) was found for nickel; the recovery of the other elements studied ranged from 60 to 70% using acid. In demineralized water, the highest lithium recovery was 14%.

Table 3

(a) Mass [mg] of valuable metals from a sample (100 mg) determined from the measured concentration after 4 hours of dissolution; (b) Comparison of the efficiency [%] of the hydrometallurgical method and with the results of our work.

(a)

	Our study				
	NMC0	NMC101	NMC201	NMC301	NMC401
Lithium in HNO₃	3.2	3.7	3.8	4.5	4.7
Lithium in demin. water	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.7	1.0
Nickel in HNO₃	13.2	14.7	16.6	23.4	28.3
Manganese in HNO₃	3.6	4.1	4.5	6.6	8.1
Cobalt in HNO₃	3.0	3.3	3.8	5.3	6.9

(b)

Methods	Leaching agent	Leaching condition	Efficiency [%]	Ref.
Hydrometallurgy	H ₂ SO ₄ + H ₂ O ₂	40 °C, 1 h	Li, Ni, Mn, Co = 99.7	[32]
	deionised water	room temperature 30-60 min	Li = 1.0	[33]
Our study	HNO ₃	pre-treated at 400 °C room temperature 4 h	Li = 69.9, Ni = 91.0, Mn = 63.6, Co = 60.4	-
	demineralized water	pre-treated at 400 °C room temperature 4 h	Li = 14.4	-

4. Discussion

The cathode sample was subjected to thermal exposure and subsequently dissolved in appropriate solvents to simulate the initial stages of the pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical process. Annealing temperatures of 100, 200, 300 and 400 °C were applied for 1 hour each, and dissolution was carried out for 1.5, 2 and 4 hours. Changes after both thermal treatment and dissolution in the specified solvents were closely monitored.

Chemical composition analysis revealed a reduction in the fluorine and phosphorus content with an increase in the temperature to which the material was exposed. This suggests that, as the temperature rises, the binder undergoes decomposition and any residual electrolyte adhering to the cathode samples is burnt off. The XRD results indicate that the material composition remains NMC622 after exposure to heat.

Examination of the samples using an SEM/EDS instrument confirmed the loss of binder with increasing temperature, as depicted in the attached photographs. Furthermore, consistent trends in chemical composition were observed, as observed in the X-ray fluorescence results - specifically, a decrease in the content of fluorine and phosphorus in the case of sample NMC401.

The TGA results confirmed that the binder decomposition occurs within the temperature range of 230 to 630 °C. This discovery implies that the material can undergo heat treatment at lower temperatures, such as 400 °C, allowing reutilization of the active material. At this temperature, most of the binder has already undergone decomposition, while the structure of the NMC remains intact. This not only minimises recycling expenses, but also ensures the feasibility of material reuse.

Measurements from ICP-OES indicated that the concentration of lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt is dependent on the dissolution time and, notably, on the temperature to which the initial material was exposed. As the temperature increased, the concentration of all elements also increased, with the highest concentration observed in the case of sample NMC401. This further supports the notion that annealing decomposed the binder, leading to the release of a higher quantify of ions into the solution from the sample subjected to the highest temperature. From the measured concentrations, the masses of dissolved ions were calculated and from these the efficiency of the process was calculated and compared to the efficiency of metal recovery from spent NMC using the hydrometallurgical method, which is the most similar in principle to our method due to the low temperatures used in our study. The theoretical efficiency of our method was similar in the case of nickel recovery (we achieved 91%), while it was lower for the other elements investigated. This is probably due to the use of a different solvent. In the compared study, sulfuric acid was used in combination with hydrogen peroxide [32]; in this work, nitric acid was used as the solvent. Although the lithium yield obtained by dissolving the material in demineralized water was fourteen times higher than in the other reported study [33], dissolution in acid gave much higher results. The higher yield obtained in our study is probably due to the longer dissolution time; on the other hand, most of the lithium is released into solution at the beginning of the process, so the heat treatment of the sample, which was carried out in this paper, will have a great influence here. Due to the highest yields at the highest temperature investigated, this work will be followed by the investigation of material fired at higher temperatures, and therefore there is the potential for further release of the binder at higher temperatures, and therefore higher yields.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the analyses, the cathode material retains its structure even when exposed to temperatures of 100-400 °C. XRD confirmed the structure of NMC622 even when the material was annealed at 400 °C. However, decomposition of the binder or leaching of electrolyte residues occurs in this temperature range, and therefore changes in composition were observed (XRF, EDS). The effect of annealing temperature is most clearly observed in the graphs showing the dependence of concentration on dissolution time, with sample NMC401 reaching the highest measured concentrations, and always after 4 hours of dissolution. From

these concentrations, the theoretical valuable metal yield was calculated, which is highest at the highest temperature investigated. From this it can be said that annealing at 400 °C for one hour followed by dissolution in 20% nitric acid for 4 hours leads to the highest yield. The efficiency of the process was 91% for nickel, while for the other metals studied it was in the range of 60-70%, which is a lower yield compared to other methods; however, nitric acid, as the solvent used is cheaper compared to other solvents used. At the same time, e.g., the pyrometallurgical method involves smelting of the material at very high temperatures (around 1500 °C), so our method could significantly reduce both the economic and environmental associated with the pre-treatment of the material. By dissolving in demineralized water, an efficiency of around 14% was achieved, which is much higher than in another study where around 1% was achieved. Therefore, dissolution in acid is more efficient in terms of yield; on the other hand, dissolution in water is a safe and economically efficient process. Since the highest yields of valuable metals were found at the highest observed annealing temperature, as well as binder decomposition, and it is therefore possible that complete binder decomposition occurs at higher temperatures, a follow-up experiment will be developed to investigate the behaviour of the same material at higher temperatures, specifically in the 500-800 °C range.

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